

Towards a new managerial approach: qualitative analysis of the role of Neuromanagement in HR performance

Vers une nouvelle approche managériale : analyse qualitative du rôle du Neuromanagement dans la performance RH.

Auteur 1 : KARIM ATIKA.

KARIM Atika (P.H.D)
School of Business and Management, (E.N.C.G), Settat, Morocco

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Abstract

Traditional human resource management is currently facing unprecedented challenges: chronic stress and burnout. To address these issues, it is becoming imperative to adopt a more scientific, innovative, and human approach. Neuromanagement, which combines neuroscience and management, aims to decode the biological mechanisms that govern our behavior at work. The article demonstrates that understanding human functioning is essential to promoting well-being at work. Qualitative analysis reveals that applying these methods can boost employee motivation and prevent burnout. In conclusion, integrating neuroscience into management practices not only reduces psychosocial risks, but also creates a resilient organization where individual fulfillment becomes the driving force behind collective success.

Keywords: Neuromanagement, Neuroscience, Well-being, Motivation, HR Performance, Human Resource Management.

Introduction

- Theoretical and Empirical Framework of the Research

In an increasingly unstable and uncertain environment, the sustainability and success of a company no longer depends solely on its technical capital, but essentially on the value it places on its human capital. However, many companies still face toxic environments where stress, unnecessary conflicts, and discontent weaken employee motivation and commitment, which directly impacts overall performance.

Organizations would therefore benefit from broadening and revisiting their traditional human resource management models. Building a modern and resilient structure requires placing people at the heart of priorities. This involves moving from administrative management to a more hands-on Human Resources function, capable of offering favorable working conditions and supporting each individual in their development. In short, placing real value on human beings is no longer just an ethical requirement, but a key success factor for any organization wishing to prosper in the long term.

Neuroscience has recently made considerable progress, enabling a complete overhaul of our understanding of human functioning. This has revolutionized the humanities and social sciences, from education to marketing and management, giving rise to new concepts that have been quickly adopted by those who hear about them (neuromanagement, neuromarketing, neuroeconomics, neuropedagogy, neurocoaching). Human resources management, in order to maintain its place within the humanities and social sciences, must take advantage of the contributions of neuroscience. The interest of neuroscience applied to management can only be greater, as it sheds new light on how we function and is useful for the well-being, motivation, decision-making, and performance of human resources within the company. This is new; science is bringing us new techniques for awareness and personal and professional development.

The temptation to revisit human resources management based on neuroscience is not a magic wand for transforming oneself, others, and the company, but it is a combination of skills and best practices that can change our vision and go beyond the limits of traditional human resource management, and even keep us up to date in a changing environment and a world characterized by the exponential growth of scientific research day after day. The idea of taking advantage of neuroscientific contributions therefore seemed quite natural, giving rise to a new avenue of HRM that merges neuroscience and management and obviously opens the door to a new world of knowledge that is none other than Neuromanagement, which explores how understanding

how the brain works can optimize leadership, decision-making, and organizational behaviors (Aithal, P. S., & Satpathy, C. P. D. J. (2024)).

Today, we are increasingly seeing the emergence of a new vision of human resources management that has emerged from a convergence between management and neuroscience, thus becoming a major asset for the success of the company of the future. This new approach aims to take into account the human being in all their complexity and diversity. It paves the way for innovation by demonstrating the effectiveness of collaboration between different fields, promoting managers' understanding of their own internal functioning and that of their employees. This new vision, which draws mainly on neuroscientific contributions, aims to study the conditions and processes that contribute to the fulfillment and well-being of individuals and the optimal functioning of companies, and to build a renewed vision of the company: it is a challenge in terms of well-being, performance, and competitiveness. The innovative contribution of this research is based on a qualitative approach that explores how Neuromanagement affects employee well-being and motivation in order to better understand its real impact on the overall performance of human resources.

- **Research Objectives and Problem Statement**

As for objectives, most research aims to explore and test (Evrard, Pras, and Roux, 1999) or explain, predict, understand, and change (Allard-Poesi and Marechal, 1999). Our research has the following main objectives:

- ✓ To determine the strength of the relationship between neuromanagement practices, well-being, motivation, and HR performance;
- ✓ To demonstrate the relevance of taking neuromanagement practices into account within the company;

In all companies, regardless of their size and/or sector of activity, work was and continues to be linked to a multitude of risks that threaten the health of employees. In order to guarantee the well-being of their resources, Moroccan companies therefore have an interest in devising a new, responsive, and flexible management style to meet the demands of a hyper-competitive and fast-paced market, but also one that is collective and attentive to its employees in order to build a strong and sustainable team. This vision envisages that, as far as possible, the workplace should be an environment that is conducive to and guarantees the well-being of employees. To achieve this result, innovative practices in neuroscience must be adopted in human resources management, emphasizing the need to offer favorable conditions and build a good social climate. In this context, our main challenge would be to answer the following question: **What**

contribution does Neuromanagement make to improving HR performance, based on the experiences of the experts consulted?

This central issue gives rise to the specific research questions presented in the figure above, which structure our exploratory approach.

Figure N°1: Research questions

Source: Personal elaboration

To address our initial problem, we felt it was important to adopt a qualitative exploratory approach that consists of discovering or deepening our understanding of a structure or functioning in order to serve two main objectives: the search for an explanation and the search for understanding. Exploration fulfills the researcher's initial intention to propose innovative theoretical results (Thiéart, 1999). It was precisely with this goal of conceptual enrichment in mind that we sought the expertise of HRM consultants and occupational psychologists during the empirical phase, in order to question their own vision and interpretation of emerging managerial practices.

- Research Structure

At the same time, research conducted within the framework of the Resource-Based Approach (Huselid, 1995 and Grinyer et al., 1990) suggests that HRM practices can have an impact on motivation and can lead to improved working conditions and social climate (well-being), which would increase productivity and HR performance. In order to articulate these theoretical and empirical dimensions, the design of our article is presented in the figure below; it is structured around three main phases.

Figure N°2: The design of the article

Source: Personal elaboration

The objective of an exploratory approach is to increase understanding of the phenomenon under study (Igalens and Roussel, 1998). In our article, this takes the form of a qualitative study using semi-structured interviews, the aim of which is to explore neuromanagement practices in a Moroccan context. To do this, we have taken the path of empirical exploration, which is adopted when the researcher is interested in phenomena that are poorly understood or even completely unknown. This approach allows us to develop new knowledge independently of previous knowledge (Thiétart et al, 2007, p.91).

The implementation of this empirical exploration approach is based on a structured methodology, which we outline in the following section through the definition of our sample, our data collection tools, and our analysis protocol.

1. The methodology of qualitative research

As part of our research, we are addressing a little-known issue, which justifies our use of qualitative exploratory research through interviews (Giordano, 2003). The aim is to explore the link between neuromanagement, well-being, motivation, and HR performance. According to Evrard et al (2003), qualitative research serves four main purposes:

- ✓ To clarify and better formulate a research problem;
- ✓ To formulate hypotheses about the relationships between variables;
- ✓ To develop and enrich a theoretical model;
- ✓ To develop measurement scales.

1.1. Qualitative research process

1.1.1 Semi-structured interviews

Our qualitative study was conducted through semi-structured or semi-directive interviews with HR consultants and occupational psychologists. Evrard et al. (2009: 91) consider that the principle of non-directivity is based on “unconditional positive regard” and an “attitude of empathy” on the part of the investigator: this involves valuing the subject's discourse and accepting their frame of reference in terms of meaning and emotion.

Rousel and Wacheux (2005) define this tool as «*a type of interview in which the researcher encourages the respondent to provide extensive, detailed, and high-quality information on the research topic, with very little influence, thereby ensuring the absence of bias and promoting scientific rigor*⁽¹⁾». According to Quivy and Van Campenhoudt (1995), interviews are a means of finding ideas, avenues for reflection, and working hypotheses, rather than a means of verifying pre-established hypotheses. The interviews lasted between 45 minutes and an hour, taking into account the recommendations of Quivy and Van Campenhoudt (1995)⁽²⁾, namely:

- ✓ The researcher should strive to ask as few questions as possible.
- ✓ The researcher should strive to formulate their interventions in as open a manner as possible.
- ✓ The researcher should refrain from getting involved in the content of the interview.
- ✓ Care should be taken to ensure that the interview takes place in an appropriate environment and context. From a technical standpoint, it is essential to record the interviews and also very useful to take a few notes from time to time.

The choice of the semi-structured interview method requires the use of a structured interview guide to address a series of topics defined in advance based on the conceptual and theoretical framework established beforehand (Albarello, 2004). With this in mind, we developed a guide consisting of three sections. We can summarize our qualitative study as follows:

Figure N°3: Qualitative study

Source: Personal elaboration

⁽¹⁾ Roussel P., Whacheux, Op.cit. Page 231

⁽²⁾ Quivy R., Van Campenhoudt L (1995), « Manuel de recherche en sciences sociales » Dunod,

Our interviews were conducted in four stages. First, we made contact with the interviewees, then we introduced the topics to be discussed, followed by a discussion of questions and points of view, and finally we concluded the interview by thanking the interviewees for their cooperation. We conducted open-ended interviews and recorded all of them on tape, which gave us more freedom to take notes and will obviously be useful in our content analysis.

1.1.2 Interview guide structure

To conduct our qualitative study, we used an interview guide to structure our interviews with occupational psychologists and HR consultants. The interview guide was built around three main themes :

Table No. 1: Structure of the interview guide

Theme No. 1	Areas of expertise of consultants and occupational psychologists.
Theme No. 2	Topics covered and nature of intervention
Theme No. 3	Neuromanagement : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stress and motivation at work • Well-being and atmosphere at work • Management and neuroscience • Manager profile

Source: Personal elaboration

The first theme aims to question interviewees about their areas of intervention and the types of companies they work with. The second theme aims to identify the subjects and themes that consultants and psychologists can address in their interventions within companies, and the nature of these interventions, such as training, seminars, skills assessments, etc.

Finally, the third and last theme constitutes the body of our research topic, namely Neuromanagement, which is composed of four sub-themes. The first sub-theme addresses stress and motivation at work, the second deals with well-being and atmosphere at work, the third is devoted to management and neuroscience, and the last theme highlights the profile of the manager.

We adopted a technique that allowed the interviewee to respond freely on the topics addressed (Baumard et al. 1999)⁽³⁾, while ensuring that the interview was framed and guided in line with the interview's objective (Grawitz, 1996)⁽⁴⁾.

⁽³⁾ Baumard, P., Donada, C., Ibert, J., & Xuereb, J. M. (2007). La collecte de données et la gestion de leurs sources (No. hal-00324538).

⁽⁴⁾ Grawitz, M. (1996). Op.cit.

1.2. Sampling and saturation principle

What is the minimum number of interviews required in a qualitative study to ensure that we remain relevant to the chosen method and research topic? This is the question asked by a researcher planning to conduct a qualitative study. According to Igalens and Roussel (1998, p.73), «*exploratory research often involves collecting data from a sample chosen for convenience or practical reasons*». The objective of this study is to provide empirical clarification, not to test a theoretical model. In selecting the sample, we based our choice on the criterion of saturation. According to Glaser and Strauss (1967), saturation is reached when each additional unit of information provides slightly less new information than the previous one, until it no longer provides anything new. It is described as «*the phenomenon that appears after a certain amount of time in qualitative research when the data collected is no longer new. All efforts to collect new information are therefore rendered useless. What we then gather falls within already known frameworks, and we can stop the research*»⁽⁵⁾ In our case, during the course of the study, we reached saturation after the seventh interview, but we thought it would be interesting to conduct an eighth interview, which did not provide any new information. We therefore interviewed a diverse range of individuals, mainly HR consultants and occupational psychologists, in order to gain an overview of our research question. We sought rich, high-quality and diverse content (Evrard et al., 2003, Giordano, 2003). We therefore took care to respect the criteria of diversity and saturation recommended for all qualitative research. The following table presents the profiles of the people interviewed.

Table No. 2: Profile of the interviewees in the qualitative study

Expert	Function	Academic Background	Years of experience
E#1	HR Consultant and Coach	Engineering– Management–HR	20 years in HR 14 years Coaching
E#2	HR and occupational psychology consultant	Doctorate in Law, HR	20 years
E#3	HR and workplace wellness consultant Neuroscience specialist	Master's degree in marketing MBA	7 years

⁽⁵⁾ Cité dans Albarello, L., (2004), Apprendre à chercher, l'acteur social et la recherche scientifique, Bruxelles : De Boeck Université., page 65

E#4	HR Consultant	HR Management	14 years
E#5	HR Consultant & coach	Management and coaching	18 years
E#6	Occupational psychologist	Work psychology	21 years
E#7	HR Consultant	HRM	12 years
E#8	HR Consultant	HRM	10 years

Source: Personal elaboration

2. Data analysis and discussion of results

2.1. Qualitative data analysis

As for the analysis of the data from our qualitative study, we chose the most appropriate method for analyzing qualitative studies, which is content analysis, as it allows us to understand a phenomenon. According to Bardin (2013), « *Content analysis is a set of communication analysis techniques aimed at obtaining indicators that allow inferences to be made about the conditions under which these messages are produced/received. Content analyses are performed on data collected using unstructured or semi-structured methods such as interviews (open-ended or semi-structured) or documentary methods. Some responses to questions included in questionnaire surveys can also be processed by content analysis. More generally, any type of verbal communication or written material can be subject to content analysis. This step is sometimes referred to as pre-analysis* ». (Bardin, 2013) cited by Thiétart et al. (2007, p.554)

According to (Bardin, 2013), there are two types of content analysis, which differ according to the unit of analysis chosen:

- ✓ Thematic analyses, which are most common in studies on organizations (Dougherty and Bowman, 1995, or D'Aveni and MacMilan, 1990). These adopt as their unit of analysis an entire sentence, parts of a sentence, or a group of sentences relating to the same theme.
- ✓ Lexical analyses adopt the word as their unit of analysis and aim to analyze the frequency of words in a text or communication.

In our study, we adopted the thematic analysis method. Below is an example of a thematic analysis of our first interview with an HR consultant and neuroscience specialist.

Table No. 3: Thematic analysis of an interview with an HR consultant and neuroscience specialist

Themes	Items	Interviews
Areas of intervention	Interventions	«Let's take a general look at: Individual performance, focused on the individual and their motivation. Relationships, which involves addressing interpersonal communication, managing difficult behaviors, and biosystemics (the impact of the system on the individual and their performance). The goal is to build a biosystemic company, i.e., one that is compatible with our biological functioning, combining well-being and performance. We also provide training in neuromanagement and neurocognitive and behavioral approaches».
Areas of intervention	Type of organization	« We work with very large and large companies, as well as medium-sized companies in all sectors without exception, depending on demand, and our services are aimed at managers, supervisors, and employees, depending on the situation».
Nature of interventions	Themes addressed	« We are called upon to intervene in a company in several cases: change management, emotion management, quality of life at work, individual and organizational performance, collective intelligence, decision-making, complexity management, etc. Our interventions cover everything related to knowledge, know-how, and interpersonal skills»

Stress and motivation	HRM challenges and their impact on employees	« Among the major problems in human resources management in Morocco, we can cite: a lack of understanding of how oneself and others function, and a failure to adapt work to people, which can lead to stress, demotivation, staff turnover, and absenteeism. In our opinion, we see that the role of the HR director is to know how to lead while taking into account how people function »
Stress	Stress and its impact on employees	« Stress is an indicator of internal inconsistency that can have impacts on several levels: emotional (flight, fight, inhibition), somatic, behavioral (lack of self-control) »
Motivation	Causes of demotivation	« We explain demotivation on three levels: <u>Individual</u> : the individual does not like their job. <u>Relational</u> : Quality of the manager (toxic manager—lack of recognition). <u>Organizational</u> : Mission impossible (average report/objectives) and/or poor information flow.».
Motivation	How to motivate ?	«Work-life balance, commitment, manager quality, love of the job, sense of belonging, company image, team spirit, personality. Managers are expected to be able to identify the sources of motivation for each employee»
Well-being	Well-being and performance	« Well-being is the reduction of stress; it is a balance between several factors and obviously influences motivation and performance».
Work atmosphere	Work environment and performance	« In our opinion and based on our experience in consulting, the work

		<i>environment should be able to influence HR motivation and performance»</i>
Management and neuroscience	Neuromanagement practices	<i>« Currently, some Moroccan companies are placing greater emphasis on human resource management, drawing on new practices (neuroscientific contributions) such as brain function, personality assessment, emotion management, stress management, etc. However, there are obstacles »</i>
Manager's profile		<i>« A leader who is capable of managing their employees while taking into account human behavior»</i>

Source: Personal elaboration

It should be noted that we adopted thematic analysis in the eight interviews and grouped the responses together.

2.2. Discussion of results and conclusion

The content analysis we adopted in our study enabled us to highlight important explanations and ideas relating to our research topic. Below, we present the results of this study in three themes: areas of intervention, topics addressed and nature of intervention, and Neuromanagement, which comprises four sub-themes.

2.2.1. Theme 1 : Areas of Intervention

According to the interviewees, interventions within companies can cover several topics depending on the company's request. They are called upon to facilitate training in personal development, provide support in HR organization or change, recruitment, and HR consulting. They generally work with large companies, multinationals, and medium-sized companies, regardless of the sector of activity. These interventions are aimed at HR directors, managers, supervisors, and employees, depending on the entity's request. The following figure (mind map) illustrates the mental representation of the areas of intervention of the people interviewed.

Figure N°4: The mental representation of the interviewees' areas of intervention

Source : Developed in EdrawMind

2.2.2. Theme 2 : Themes Addressed

According to the people interviewed, they address a multitude of topics, which we present in the figure below:

Figure N°5: Mental representation of the themes addressed by the interviewees

Source: Developed in EdrawMind

These interventions therefore focus on three areas: knowledge, know-how, and interpersonal skills. In this sense, E#3 states, «Our interventions focus primarily on everything related to

behavior and mindset». They can take the form of seminars (awareness-raising, staff days, communication initiatives), training (skills acquisition), team building (change management, strategic projects), skills assessments (strategy development, HR master plan, etc.), support sessions (professional support, targeted and/or specialized training, coaching, etc.). We therefore see that companies call on consultants and psychologists when their managers and HR directors find themselves in very specific professional situations and when they have to deal with individual, relational, managerial, or organizational issues.

2.2.3. Theme 3: From People Management to Neuromanagement

The main objective of our study was to ask respondents about HRM issues in Morocco and to find out how consultants perceive neuromanagement practices.

- Perception of Stress and Motivation

In relation to HRM issues in Morocco, analysis of the interviews revealed various problems. In response to the question «*What do you think are the problems with HRM?* », the interviewees cited several, the most recurrent of which were: lack of understanding of how others work, failure to adapt work to people, understaffing, inequality in the distribution of the workload, growing apparent and latent conflicts, lack of fairness in the remuneration of efforts, abnormally high levels of stress, and a deteriorated social climate. This may be caused by the lack of an HR strategy, the weak or very limited power of the HR department, the absence or deficiency of HR evaluation, the dysfunction of the recruitment process, the inconsistency or dysfunction of the motivation system, and the mentality, culture, and practices inherited from our habits. This can have direct or indirect influences on HR, including demotivation, lack of involvement, a sense of not belonging, low performance, routine, workplace accidents, chronic stress, turnover, and absenteeism.

In response to questions about stress, its causes, and its impact on HR, respondents defined stress as a state of pressure exceeding the level of skills required to manage such a situation. The definition was clearly highlighted in the following statements:

«*Stress is the perception of an imaginary threat to the ego, causing the person to function in automatic instinct mode*». E#1

«*An organism's response to danger, it is an indicator of internal inconsistency, which is caused by the quality of the boss, the social climate, and the person themselves*». E#3

«*Stress is poor work organization*». E#2

Furthermore, we raised during the thematic analysis that the impacts of stress are diverse and are outlined in the following figure:

Figure N°6: Mental Representation of Stress Impacts on HR

Source: Developed in EdrawMind

As for motivation, we asked two questions. The first was: «**In your opinion, how can employee demotivation be explained?** » The second was: «**In your opinion, how can an employee be motivated to give their best for the company?** » When analyzing the data, we found that demotivation is the result of, among other things:

- ✓ Loss of meaning for the individual,
- ✓ Unmet needs,
- ✓ Perception of injustice or unfairness,
- ✓ Lack of prospects for the future,
- ✓ Quality of management and managers (toxic manager)
- ✓ Lack of recognition
- ✓ Impossible tasks
- ✓ Poor communication
- ✓ Company culture

In response to the second question, **E#5** suggests: «*In my opinion, and in short, it is in the hierarchy's best interest to listen to employees in order to identify: their perceptions of their work, their actual needs, and their suggestions for improving their motivation.* » This statement was confirmed by the other respondents.

- Well-being & Work Atmosphere

All the consultants and psychologists interviewed agree on the importance of well-being at work and the working environment. As can be seen in the comments of **E#1**, who states: *«I think that well-being at work is relative and varies according to objective variables in the organizational environment. In other words, it depends on each individual case. Nevertheless, I can highlight the importance of the following elements: A work environment that values all organizational stakeholders, a management style that unleashes potential and capitalizes on talent, a human values system consistent with the organization's mission, and balanced relationships that combine the human and professional dimensions»*. **E#2** also states that *«A person feels good at work when they have a real sense of belonging»*. In part **E#6**, it states that *«Well-being is a balance between several factors, including reduced stress»*.

With regard to the working environment, all interviewees confirmed that well-being and the working environment should influence employee motivation and performance. In this regard, **E#7** states that *«Management is largely responsible for employee motivation, in the sense that it has the power to influence employees positively to improve performance»*. These findings are consistent with those in the literature, in which the work environment appears to be a determining factor that inevitably influences well-being and HR performance.

- Management and neuroscience

According to the views of consultants interviewed on human resource management in Morocco, the role of the HR function, and the practices put in place to manage human capital, companies, especially large ones and some SMEs, are aware of the importance of human capital. That is why they are striving to review their human resource management strategies by implementing new practices. We can see these ideas reflected in the comments of some consultants reported below:

«Overall, regulations in this area have undergone enormous change. Nowadays, there is a real awareness of the importance of human capital. This promises a bright future for HR. I remain optimistic about the change projects that are beginning to be implemented and that aim to shift managerial practice towards true HRM». **E#1**

«The practices I have observed within our Moroccan organizations include: acquisition and MEP of HRIS, MEO of GPEEC, implementation and MEP of REC, MEO of the performance evaluation and skills assessment process, implementation of skills assessments, development of continuing education plans, regular organization of continuing education activities, and development and MEP of REC». **E#1**

«I think Moroccan companies are aware of the importance of continuous development in HRM, as a support function that uses new practices to manage human capital, but this is the case for institutional companies and not family businesses. Among the practices I can cite as examples are: the 360° method, GETEC, and matrix organization». E#4

In the literature, many authors discuss the contributions and benefits of neuromanagement practices (David Rock, 2009; Patrick Collignon and Chantal Vander Vorst, 2013; Cécile Schauer, 2014). Indeed, taking neuroscientific contributions into account (human functioning, emotion management, stress management, personalities, etc.) can be an added value for human management, so it is important to understand the human beings within the company. These two observations constitute two central questions in our interview guide. The interviewees' responses evoke the following comments:

«HR is the key to everything within an organization. Nothing gets done without it... Neuroscience has proven itself in the West and, in my opinion, is a reliable and very promising lever for the development of our human resources. It can offer concrete, practical, inexpensive, and high-value-added solutions that increase performance and promote well-being. In this case, it would involve training and supporting HR in order to change its paradigms and raise its skill levels». E#1

«In my opinion, it is important to understand the human beings within the company, but this is not an easy task at all». E#8

In response to the question, *«Can you give us an idea of what Neuromanagement is? »* The majority of consultants expressed almost the same idea, which posits that Neuromanagement is the management of human resources based on the contributions of cognitive science, or that it is an approach whose objective is to take into account how human beings function in the corporate sphere.

- Profile of a good manager

In addition to their technical skills, managers need to develop: their personality, their managerial skills, and their emotional intelligence. This is the conclusion we drew from the interviewees' comments.

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